

One more conjecture about prime numbers

Conjecture 1. There is no equation of the form $f(a, b, c, d, g, h, i, l, n) = an^g + bn^h + cn^i + \dots + dn^l$, where $a, b, c, d, g, h, i, l, n \in \mathbb{R}$ that generates only prime numbers.